

THE IMPORTANCE OF VICTIMOLOGICAL PREVENTION IN CRIME PREVENTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7578297>

Abstract. The article presents the investigation of crime prevention. It also deals with the importance of victimological prevention. The results of the research depicted that victimology is considered as important part of crime prevention.

Keywords: victimology, prevention, crime, types, characteristics, analysis.

The term "victimology" is a combination of the Latin word *victima* - "victim" and the Greek word *logos* - "doctrine", which means the doctrine of the victim. Victimology includes the general doctrine of victims, that is, not only the victims of crimes, but also the victims of various negative situations, accidents, natural disasters, wars, etc.[5.247-248].

Humanity, forgiveness, and tolerance are the ancient values of our people. That is why the principles of our statehood, the mutual agreement between the person who committed the crime and the victim, are widely used. In his case, since the person who committed the crime paid compensation to the victim, the injured party had the right to forgive him and ask the judge (court) to release the guilty person from punishment. For example, Burhoniddin Marginani's work "Hidaya" states that after the compensation is used as a punishment, the culprit must pay it within three years.

The Italian criminologist Raffaele Garofalo (1852-1934) viewed restitution as a means of strengthening the public's protection against criminals.[2.18-19].

German criminologist Sarah Marjorie Frye (1894-1958) in her researches identified the reconciliation of the criminal with the victim as a factor in stabilizing order and harmony in society.[4].

It should be noted that the doctrine of the victim plays an important role in the study of the causes of crime. Also, it is important not to forget that scientific knowledge of the role of the victim in the commission of the crime is of great importance in the development of crime prevention measures.

It is self-evident that the main goal of the study of criminal victimology is to determine and study the role and importance of the crime victim in the occurrence of certain crimes, the "contribution" to the occurrence and development of the criminal situation. For this, it is necessary to obtain general information about the identity of the victim, as well as about his behavior before committing the crime.[3].

It is also important to study the occurrence of victim situations. Victimhood is the social, physical and moral qualities, characteristics and behavior of a certain person that caused him to become a victim of crime in certain situations.

Several types of victimization are distinguished in the literature:

- 1) individual victimhood - according to the social, biophysiological and mental characteristics of a certain person, he commits a crime in certain life situations and inflicts a certain amount of damage on himself;
- 2) co-occurring victimization - the "tendency" of some individuals to suffer from certain types of crime (for example, robbery, defamation, etc.) under the influence of several circumstances;
- 3) group victimhood - the ability of people with similar social, demographic, psychological, biophysical and other characteristics to be victims of crimes characteristic of similar categories (collectors, guards, taxi drivers, etc.);
- 4) mass victimization - a certain part of the population objectively suffers from crimes due to their subjective characteristics.[1].

One of the main factors in the listed cases of victimization is the specific characteristics of the victim. It should be noted that not only subjective characteristics of a person but also other factors affect a person's falling into a state of victimhood. That is, a person may suffer from a crime not because of his personal characteristics, but as a result of their combination and connection with other factors.

Criminal victimology research is more effective when conducted on the basis of crime types. Such research provides the opportunity to acquire necessary information about the state of victimization, the factors that cause victimization, to study and know the relationship between victim behavior and criminal behavior, and through this, to develop measures for the prevention of crimes.

For this reason, the study of some types of crime is currently being conducted more widely and actively. In this context, two main issues are cross-cutting.

Victimological studies are able to significantly expand the possibilities of studying the causes and conditions of crime, its composition, and assessing the general negative consequences of crime. However, the role of victimology has not yet been adequately evaluated. The official statistical reports do not contain any relevant indicators about the victims. Laws have not been adopted on the victims, their rights and duties, methods and forms of compensation for the damage caused to them. There is no special section (chapters) on victims, on proper assessment of the victim's identity and behavior in the investigation and in court in the criminal procedural law.

Conclusion. Considering all the information into account, it can be concluded that victimology includes the general doctrine of victims, that is, not only the victims of crimes, but also the victims of various negative situations, accidents, natural disasters. Criminal victimology is to determine and study the role and importance of the crime victim in the occurrence of certain crimes, the "contribution" to the occurrence and development of the criminal situation. Therefore, it is essential to conduct victimological prevention before happening crimes.

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